

Object Detection Using Deep Learning

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Object Detection is a one of the interesting challenges of computer vision. Not only the object should be classified to a certain class but also its exact location is determined within a frame.

A straightforward way to accomplish this is to apply a sliding window on the frame and applying the classifier at each given location of the sliding window. Unfortunately, this technique is not practical as it will be exhaustive in time thus difficult to apply in real time even when using a simple classifier that uses HoG features.

A more practical approach is achieved using Deep Learning. Deep learning-based object detectors do end-to-end object detection.

2. Aim

To understand the current trends in Object Detection using Deep Learning.

3. Material and methods

A conceptual understanding of object Detection
Today benchmark object Detection Framework
Object Detection as a classification problem
Object Detection as a regression problem
Object Detection using Region Proposal Networks●
Object Detection using Fast-RCNN
Object Detection using Faster-RCNN
Object Detection using YoLo

4. Conclusions

The attendances will understand the main techniques in objects detection and the limitation of each one of the presented approaches

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5. Keywords

Deep Learning, Computer Vision

Author biography

Walid Ahmed Experienced Professor with a demonstrated history of working in the higher education

industry.

Skilled in Deep learning, Machine Learning , Python and Java .

Strong quality assurance professional with a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) focused in Electrical and Electronics Engineering from Faculty of engineering